

Jewish Catacomb Bibliography Notes 2 (2012):

Elsa Laurenzi, *Le catacombe ebraiche*.
 Gli ebrei di Roma e le loro tradizioni funerarie,
 Gangemi Editore, Rome, 2011/*Jewish
 Catacombs. The Jews of Rome: funeral rites
 and customs*, Gangemi Editore, Rome, 2013

The publication of Elsa Laurenzi's *Le Catacombe Ebraiche* in 2011 inspired a conference in late February of the following year on current research on the Jewish catacombs of Rome. As Laurenzi's book is, in essence, a comprehensive introduction to this area of study, and reasonably cautious on all counts, it is the conference itself, involving a great diversity of perspectives and experiences, which has the most potential to inspire new research and debate on these sites. For this reason, Laurenzi's work is considered along with what was discussed at the event. The link to the conference video is: <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q2LKZootsLk>.

In her introduction to "Le Catacombe Ebraiche," the moderator, Dr. Micaela Vitale, Adult Education Director at the Pitigliani Jewish Cultural Center in Rome (<http://www.pitigliani.it>), expresses great pleasure in speaking about a matter very "dear to her heart." She reveals that the Jewish catacombs were one of the first topics she researched as a young archaeologist in Rome nearly thirty years ago, in 1984, as the maintenance of these sites was in the process of being transferred to the Italian State. Vitale also reminds the audience that even now these catacombs are not completely accessible and open to the public on a regular basis. Much work remains to be done.

Vitale then goes on to present the panelists, each of whom is asked to address a different aspect of these sites. First is Danilo Mazzoleni, Professor of Epigraphy at the Pontificio Istituto di Archeologia Cristiana and Università di Roma Tre. Vitale praises Mazzoleni as "instrumental in her own formation as an archaeologist and scholar," sharing vivid memories of a tour he led of the Jewish Epigraphic Collection in the Vatican Museums in 1984. The second panelist is Stefano Tortorella, professor of Greek and Roman Art at the Università degli Studi di Roma "La Sapienza," and former colleague of Vitale on a number of archaeological digs. A specialist in material culture and Roman paintings, Tortorella is invited to discuss examples of Imperial-era funerary painting in the Jewish catacombs of Rome. Dr. Riccardo Di Segni, Chief Rabbi of Rome, is also present to clarify the nature of Jewish funerary rites and the continuing obligation to respect Jewish bodily remains.

The author, Dr. Elsa Laurenzi (6:12-16:47), provides a brief introduction to the study of Jewish catacombs in Rome by focusing on the Vigna Randanini and Villa

Torlonia sites, although with passing mention of research in course in the catacombs of the Monteverde. An art historian by training, she notes that the wall paintings in these underground cemeteries contain a combination of themes and motifs “typical of painting in that period,” and can be dated on stylistic grounds to the end of the third century and beginning of the fourth century CE (with the exception of the well-preserved examples in what Laurenzi calls the “Pegasus” cubiculum in the Vigna Randanini, possibly a century earlier in date).

As in the lecture, Laurenzi’s book manages to be both descriptive and synthetic, above all with a “virtual tour” of the five known Jewish catacomb sites, three of which survive relatively intact (Vigna Randanini, Villa Torlonia, and Vigna Cimarra). It contains many “user friendly” elements like maps and photographs and definitions within the text of important vocabulary terms. Yet, on occasion, Laurenzi’s statements on catacomb topography need clarification, particularly in regards to the site she knows very well, that of the Vigna Randanini. For instance, while a number of the kokhim in area D might have been enlarged in a later phase of excavation, as Laurenzi suggests (p. 50), access to the inner galleries and funerary chambers would still have been through the original kokh. Would any burials have been disturbed to make such changes? Or does this detail suggest to Laurenzi that secondary burials were made inside these kokhim? A full skeleton inside an intact kokh does not support this practice.

For that matter, Laurenzi describes the “forno” tombs in the inner chamber of the “Pegasus Cubiculum” (figure) as posterior to the phase during which the space was decorated with paintings (p. 54). Given the distinct cut of the “forno” tombs as originally excavated, however, and what Mazzoleni has identified in the past as traces of a red border around the mouths of these tombs, it is not impossible that these, too formed part of the chamber’s original plan, in a manner similar to the arrangement of two “forno” tombs on the back wall of another anonymous catacomb in the area of “Roma Vecchia” (unfortunately, the tomb at left in the Randanini cubiculum, not subject to later modifications for additional burials as was the case for the tomb at right, is now sealed by the inscription CIJ 1.149/JIWE 2.223, not in this location when first found).

Laurenzi's plan of the Randanini cemetery on p. 49 does not integrate the interesting results of a recent topographical survey by the "Roma Sotterranea" organization (S. Lombardi, "La catacomba ebraica di Vigna Randanini," *Forma Urbis* 14.12 (2009), pp. 4-14). In her own plan, Laurenzi identifies a variety of different excavations or phases of excavation (A-F; g-i), but does not explain, on p. 51, the origins of gallery E, which connects to three other areas of the site (D - e - F). What she labels "e", situated at about 2 m. above the current

floor level in E is, in fact, the corner of a small cubiculum that connects to a gallery filled with dirt and structural debris. It is very unlikely that E later developed from this point. In addition, what is labeled F2 is actually quite distinct from the other two areas labeled F on Laurenzi's plan, and could very well have developed from a separate entry point. Two other details are also represented incorrectly. The "Cubiculum of the Menorah" (f) discussed on pp. 37-38, is not the chamber preceded by the long *dromos* in area F on Laurenzi's plan. Furthermore, contrary to what Laurenzi says on p. 52, we do know of a small number of funerary goods recovered from the site during excavations from 1859-1862 and again in 1882, although the current whereabouts of these artifacts is unknown.

The bibliography at the end of this volume has a curious mix of "classic" and very contemporary works (including an article in press by Cinzia Vismara and unpublished theses by Laurenzi herself and a colleague, Tommaso Bergamo, from the "La Sapienza" University of Rome). Given that some of these were written just before the book's publication in 2011, it is not clear why other works specifically on the Jewish catacombs of Rome have been excluded, notably Silvia Cappelletti's 2006 monograph, *The Jewish Community in Rome from the Second Century BCE to the Third Century CE*, and a number of recent articles by Leonard V. Rutgers (on a personal note, my articles emerged after Laurenzi's book was already in press). Yet, in all fairness, Laurenzi's work arrives at a pivotal moment when many new studies are being conducted in these sites. It would be virtually impossible for any one text to remain current with all the information on Jewish catacombs just now coming to light.

Rabbi Riccardo Di Segni (16:47-29:45) next offers his thoughts on the nature of the ancient funerary rites that could have taken place inside the Jewish catacombs of Rome, finding the presence of *kokhim* in certain areas of the Vigna Randanini catacomb particularly significant for their semblance to graves in Israel used for an

initial deposition of the corpse before the bones were collected and put into smaller spaces or containers (figure).

In this process, the kokhim in Israel were not entirely sealed, since an opening would have been left by the head in case burial had been premature, although this, too, would eventually have been closed (Di Segni does not associate this detail, however, to any specific evidence from the kokhim in Rome). In Di Segni's view, the Roman kokhim are very

“real testimonies” to religious practices of the Diaspora Jews otherwise known exclusively from very limited textual sources. He also emphasizes the great “patrimony of inscriptions” from the catacombs naming those who served in the hierarchy of these communities, although with scarce note of any rabbis in their midst. Yet aside from the contents of the six hundred or so funerary inscriptions for the most part in Greek, and the images of menorot, items for the celebration of Sukkoth, and objects of a more uncertain nature that decorate a variety of artifacts in these sites, evidence of Jewish religious practice is, at best, limited to a small number of structural details and the overall impression that, for a certain period of time, the men, women, and children laid to rest in these cemeteries specifically sought burial next to other Jews. Di Segni therefore defines these individuals as “Jewish, with unique ways of assimilating into another culture.”

On the issue of literary evidence, Di Segni brings up a topic greatly debated in recent years: the total number of Jews in Ancient Rome during the Imperial period. The Jewish catacombs (including those no longer intact) contain, at most, a few thousand burials. Yet literary sources somewhat earlier in date state far higher numbers of Jews. To Di Segni, it may be a case of rhetorical exaggeration, for even now “if you ask on the street today how many Jews there are in Rome you might get the answer - a couple of million.” On the other hand, he points out that, in reality, we don't even know how many Jewish catacombs there were, or whether there were other systems of burial also in use. One of his final comments sums up the current state of research very concisely: “the things that we don't know are far more than those we do know (about these sites).”

Particularly fascinating is Di Segni's measured commentary on what concerns him directly in his role as Chief Rabbi of Rome: the modern religious observances of the Jews and how these factor into the maintenance and preservation of the ancient cemetery sites. Even after centuries of neglect and vandalism, the catacombs still contain many human remains (although a small number of animal bones have been identified in the Vigna Randanini site – notably a cow's skull in area F). Jewish Law dictates that even after a millennium and a half or more, in whatever state of preservation, these, too, need to be conserved. Restoration of areas where bones

are clearly visible, in apparent desecration of the original tombs (especially in the Villa Torlonia catacomb, where many bones have fallen onto the narrow gallery floor) is a delicate matter, and has been discussed at length by Jewish religious authorities with largely positive results. The removal of bones from a Jewish grave is no longer treated as a casual matter, as in the case of the - presumably unauthorized - modern ossuary in the Vigna Randanini catacomb inside the well shaft at the entrance to area F.

Perhaps in light of the damage already done, some Jews have moved to adopt extreme measures to protect the tombs (<http://www.timesofmalta.com/articles/view/20090222/local/jewish-bones-in-rabat-are-ours.245955>). The Jewish organization Zaka attempted to intervene in the on-going restorations in the Villa Torlonia catacomb in 2008, risking the total blockage of all work in the site (<http://www.zaka.org.uk/news.asp?AID=59>). To Rome's Chief Rabbi at that time and others, Zaka's demands eventually became too extreme, and a compromise was sought on safeguarding the ancient Jewish tombs. In the end, Di Segni relates, it was an eighty-year-old rabbi from London, an expert on Jewish doctrine and principles, who finally provided guidelines most compatible with the work of the archaeologists in Rome. Di Segni, a medical doctor by training, admits to being somewhat skeptical at first of the elderly rabbi's techniques, for when asked for advice about the presence of tombs in the galleries, the rabbi simply began walking though the site with two short metal wands in an L-shaped formation. To Di Segni's astonishment, the sticks apparently came together to form an "X" each time there was a hollow space, presumably a grave, below floor level, and the Roman rabbi says he even tried dowsing himself to see how such unconventional methods could work. The matter was thus resolved though divination: all human remains are to be covered completely in these sites, but the bones from the more damaged areas can be moved to safer zones, such as the nearest loculus. As a result, work has been able to continue in the Torlonia site, which could soon be open to the public on a regular basis due to its proximity to Rome's new Holocaust Museum.

Danilo Mazzoleni (31:40 –49:40) is still remembered as a sort of ambassador between the Pontifical Archaeological Commission and international Jewish communities during the decade of negotiations before the Jewish catacombs were officially consigned to Italy in 1984. His first survey on these sites was published in 1975, at the start of his academic career, and some decades later he continues to include the study of Jewish epigraphy in his fundamental survey at the PIAC of Christian epigraphy from all parts of the Roman world. A characteristic of Mazzoleni's approach is the critical review of a "bibliografia essenziale," of the most reliable sources for the Jewish inscriptions and the contexts in which these artifacts were originally found. Not surprisingly, in a wave of new studies on these sites, this exercise can easily last an entire class period or more, and must address the work of social and religious historians as well as that of epigraphists. Particularly effective are his practices of bringing the actual books to class to draw attention to the strengths – and sometimes weaknesses - of each source, and manner of illustrating

the many parallels between Jewish and non-Jewish funerary texts produced in Rome.

While fairly conservative in his own work on the Jewish catacombs, Mazzoleni consistently regards the inscriptions from these sites in a much broader context, and during the Laurenzi presentation was able to illustrate many “communal elements” in the Jewish and Christian catacomb inscriptions in terms of their language, content, and appearance, although a number also contain unique information about the offices and positions held by members of Jewish and Christian communities in Rome. This detail becomes particularly significant in terms of the 600 or so funerary inscriptions regarded as Jewish: these represent, in fact, almost all of our primary source material on Jews in Rome at this time.

Defining Laurenzi’s book as the first “general overview” of the Jewish catacombs in Rome for a wide readership, Mazzoleni compliments Laurenzi on making the distinction between “objective data” and “working hypotheses,” a very complicated task in light of current debate on the Jewish catacombs’ origins, development, and eventual abandonment. Yet he does not shy away from addressing many points of contention, often drawing upon so-called pagan or Christian practices to illustrate what might have also been the case in Rome for many Jews. Regarding the lack of material evidence for Jewish places of worship in the city, Mazzoleni voices the theory that gatherings of the synagogues could have been held in private homes, although the monumental remains of synagogue halls have been found in other areas of Italy, notably at Ostia Antica and Bova Marina. Anticipating the question as to where Jews would have been buried in Rome before the development of extensive subterranean burial grounds beginning in the late second century CE, Mazzoleni believes it entirely possible that Jews “mixed” with non-Jews in the larger Roman necropoli and, depending on their social station as freedmen or slaves, could even have joined the gentiles in columbaria. Communal burial sites may have become more popular as Jews sought to enlarge burial plots already in use and make more adequate provisions for the poor. Needless to say, this is still an issue hotly debated, with some adhering to the centuries-old belief that Jews actually started the whole practice of excavating catacombs in Rome, or at least used this form of burial much earlier than the Christians did.

Describing Jewish epigraphic production in Rome, and especially the thorny question of dating, Mazzoleni focuses on data from the three major catacomb sites – Vigna Randanini, Villa Torlonia, and Monteverde. As a good number of the artifacts from these sites are seen today out of context in museums and other collections, knowing their provenance is critical, for without this information, certain inscriptions like CIJ 1.219 & 240, “would never be seen as Jewish.” Given the neutral elements in many epitaphs from the “Jewish” sites, it must have been up to the individual client to decide which expressions or images to use in commemoration of the deceased. This could, in fact, help explain why the Jewish inscriptions take on certain “stereotypical” features of the Roman epigraphic production in Greek and Latin during the third and fourth centuries CE (only a very small percentage of the

inscriptions – about 1% - are written with Hebrew script). Quoting Vitale, Mazzoleni notes that it might also reflect that among the Jews

themselves, “Greek was the everyday language of the street, Latin the official tongue, and Hebrew used for religious/ritual use” (Vitale, 1994), although it is also very likely that Greek was the predominant language for worship for a number of these groups (Cappelletti, 2006). Most of the inscriptions are created in the capitalis actuaria rustica script also characteristic of Christian epigraphic production of the third and fourth centuries CE; in all probability, the same stonecutters did the work for both groups. Mazzoleni adds, however, that in the opinion of Fr. Antonio Ferrua, inscriptions of such uncertain composition could also date primarily to the fourth century CE (Ferrua, 1936). It is in this late period, in fact, that Latin becomes the language most commonly used, although it is found in only 7% of the total number of Jewish inscriptions from Rome, perhaps because burials had already started to become less frequent in catacomb sites.

Beyond textual concerns is the presence of what are generally called “symbols” on a little less than half of all the Jewish inscriptions from Rome. Mazzoleni elaborates on an idea first expressed by Fr. Umberto M. Fasola, B. that the representations of Jewish cult objects such as the menorah, ethrog, lulab, shofar, aron, oil vase, knife, etc., should be seen as more representational or figurative than symbolic. Only rarely does he find a more “symbolic language” using these cult objects actually expressed, as in the case of an unusual anepigraphic marble fragment (now missing) from the Vigna Cimarra catacomb (CIJ 1.281a) decorated with what appears to be a lion defending the Jewish Law. Mazzoleni does not add, however, that this composition is actually quite similar to what is represented on a number of gold glass bases from Rome (CIJ 1.516 & 517), that often provide a full “sampling” of the Jewish cult objects mentioned above (particularly in the case of the gold glass CIJ 1.520, in which the lintel of the aron is decorated with the shofar, menorah, and ethrog).

In addition to the explicitly Jewish elements, there are instances when baskets of flowers or fruits, animals, and trees accompany Jewish inscriptions, and a number of sarcophagi are embellished with distinctly non-traditional objects, like CIJ 1.1 and the “sarcophagus of the seasons” relief now on display in the National Roman Museum.

Mazzoleni concludes that the epigraphic evidence is of primary

importance, although many open questions remain. We still know little about the nature and duration of the various offices and titles awarded to individuals connected to the synagogues (and, on occasion, more than one synagogue). We cannot establish the “orthodoxy” of these Roman Jews of the third and fourth centuries CE (hardly the only generations of Jews to have made their home in this city!) based on select evidence from their tombs, for certain words and phrases may or may not have distinctly Jewish meanings. Yet without these testimonies from the catacombs, we would have a far less detailed picture about the Jews in Ancient Rome.

For conference co-organizer, Prof. Stefano Tortorella (50-114), the occasion is “truly a pleasurable meeting among old friends,” not only the panelists themselves but also members of the audience including Prof. Cinzia Vismara of the University of Cassino, one of Laurenzi’s thesis advisors and the author of several studies on the Jewish catacombs of Rome, and Dr. Maria Rosaria Barbera, the newly-appointed Archaeological Superintendent of Rome and former inspector of the Nomentana region where two of the Jewish catacombs are found. In Tortorella’s view, it is to no small degree the work of these scholars and others that has inspired the great “fervor of studies” on these sites.

Tortorella, on his part, emphasizes that the harsh Roman political policies affecting the area of ancient Palestine did not necessarily reflect the situation of the Jews in Rome, for it does not appear that “Jews and Romans were not locked in an eternal struggle in this latter arena.” The Jews of this time are known, in fact, from both Jewish and non-Jewish literary sources, to have had friends in high places, even in the imperial palace itself (notably the Empress Poppaea and members of the Severan dynasty). Regarding the nature of Jewish burial in Rome, however, Tortorella is in agreement that there is no evidence for an “autonomous administration of (Jewish) funerary sites” before the end of second century or beginning of third century CE, and the “society of death can reflect society of the living,” in the sense that the Jewish catacombs, in terms of their location, appearance and use, reflected the typical modes of burial in Rome at that time.

Like Laurenzi, Tortorella has worked extensively on the history of Roman painting, and provides a number of insights into the surviving pictorial decoration in the Vigna Randanini and Villa Torlonia sites. Identifying the content as a “mix of myths, Jewish themes, and Greco-Roman motifs,” Tortorella argues that the images found in these sites, objects of great controversy in the past, might not have seemed quite so offensive to ancient Jews. The “Pegasus” hypogeum, created around the early third century CE, could have been integrated into the Jewish cemetery at a later point because the subject matter of its paintings was, in fact, quite “elastic” – even the personifications of Abundance or Plenty and Victory in the act of crowning a young man (figure). For Tortorella, Late Antique painting is characterized by such flexibility in content and form, and could therefore produce examples that incorporate both Jewish and Classical motifs, as in the case of the cubiculum decorated with dolphins and Jewish objects in the Villa Torlonia, or instances when

Greco-Roman motifs appear to take on a distinctly Jewish significance, like those in the Vigna Randanini's "Cubiculum of the Palms," a colorfully decorated chamber unfortunately much damaged by later tombs (figure). Like Mazzoleni, Tortorella presents the Jewish catacombs in a global context – quite literally, for he compares certain decorative motifs on the side walls of the monumental arcosolia in the Villa Torlonia to those in a fourth century CE non-Jewish funerary cubiculum far from Rome – near Silistra, in fact, on the border between Bulgaria and Romania, Rome's outermost frontier. We know from literary sources of the Jews' access to the rich and famous in Rome,

but here we also see that a number of Jews were able to commission the high-quality paintings favored by many of Rome's elite.

Tortorella rapidly concludes the conference with the hope that the new attention on the Jewish catacombs will contribute toward their conservation as important cultural sites. This already appears to be taking place in the Torlonia catacomb, despite the many structural and environmental challenges to address, and the Vigna Randanini site, too, has enjoyed a great surge in popularity. The Vigna Cimarra and what might remain below the Monteverde have far less potential, in terms of their accessibility, but there is no doubt that much more can and should be done to increase our understanding of these sites.

I personally was quite moved by what happened just as the conference was ending and the panelists were getting up to leave. At this point, a man approached the table and mentioned the work of an American "professoressa di archeologia," Estelle Brettman, whose research on the Vigna Randanini and Villa Torlonia catacombs had once been on display in the Castel Sant'Angelo Museum in Rome (figure). The

woman in question was none other than the founder of the International Catacomb Society in Boston, an organization that has done much over the past three decades to raise international awareness of the Jewish catacombs in Rome. It is interesting and somewhat ironic that Brettman's name was brought up at the end of a discussion of new research on these sites, for without her advocacy, important artifacts and discoveries inside of these catacombs might not now be known.

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